

GENERALIZED PROBABILISTIC NEURAL NETWORK BASED CLASSIFIERS

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Abstract

Two new Probabilistic Neural Network (PNN) based maximum likelihood classifiers are presented. These classifiers are based on Gram-Charlier series expansion with/without Parzen's windowing technique. The performances of the proposed classifiers are evaluated in terms of probability of target detection for a number of Gaussian and non-Gaussian noises, and compared with those of the existing neural network classifiers such as Bayesian and Backpropagation classifiers. The new proposed neural network classifiers perform better than existing classifiers in radar target detection. These classifiers are also applicable to many more practical situations than Specht's Bayesian classifier.

1. Introduction

Neural Networks (NN) have the potential for solving difficult problems without knowing in advance the solution methodology. One such problem is signal detection in non-Gaussian noises. Neural networks may potentially offer good detection performance compared with conventional techniques because of their ability for near real time parallel processing, adaptability, and training using real data. In these new classifiers neural networks are used to estimate probability density function of the input data and these density functions are used to perform maximum likelihood detection. A neural network based Bayesian classifier was proposed by Specht [2]. However this method has the following limitations: (1) It requires normalized inputs (2) all input data has to have same power level (3) probability density functions for all classes need to have the same covariance matrix (4) it applies only to symmetric noises and (5) it requires a large buffer to store the training samples. The classifiers presented in this paper will overcome many limitations of Specht's method and hence will be applicable to many more practical situations.

2. Generalized Probabilistic Neural Networks

Two Generalized Probabilistic Neural Networks are proposed for use as optimum classifiers. The first proposed method uses Gram-Charlier series expansion without the Parzen's windowing technique to estimate the underlying pdf of the data available for training. These pdfs are then used to form a maximum likelihood classifier. This classifier is further discussed in section 3. The second proposed method uses the Gram-Charlier series expansion with a Parzen's windowing technique to estimate the underlying pdf from the training data. This classifier is further discussed in section 4.

2.1. A Brief Description of Gram-Charlier Series Expansion (GCSE)

The probability density function $p(x)$ of a random variable X can be expanded in Gram-Charlier series as

$$p(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} c_i \phi^{(i)}\left(\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma}\right) \quad (1)$$

where μ and σ^2 are the mean and the variance of X and $\phi(x)$ is a Gaussian density function. The coefficients c_i 's are given by

$$c_0 = 1, c_1 = c_2 = 0, c_3 = \frac{-1}{3!} \alpha_3, c_4 = \frac{1}{4!} (\alpha_4 - 3), c_5 = \frac{-1}{5!} (\alpha_5 - 10\alpha_3), c_6 = \frac{1}{6!} (\alpha_6 - 15\alpha_4 + 30),$$

where α_i is the i^{th} central moment of $p(x)$. The α_i 's are related to noncentral moments m_k 's by $\alpha_3 = \frac{m_3 - 3m_2m_1 + 2m_1^3}{\sigma^3}$, $\alpha_4 = \frac{m_4 - 4m_3m_1 + 6m_2m_1^2 - 3m_1^4}{\sigma^4}$, $\alpha_5 = \frac{m_5 - 5m_4m_1 + 10m_3m_1^2 - 10m_2m_1^3 + 4m_1^5}{\sigma^5}$, $\alpha_6 = \frac{m_6 - 6m_5m_1 + 15m_4m_1^2 - 20m_3m_1^3 + 15m_2m_1^4 - 5m_1^6}{\sigma^6}$, where $m_k = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^k$. It can be shown that the coefficients c_i 's for $i > 6$ are small. Thus, c_i 's for $i > 6$ can be neglected. It can also be shown that $\phi^{(i)}(x)$ is equal to $\frac{1}{(2\pi\sigma^2)^{1/2}\sigma} e^{-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}} H_i\left(\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma}\right)$, where the Hermit polynomials $H_i(y)$'s are given by, $H_0(y) = 1$, $H_1(y) = y$, $H_2(y) = y^2 - 1$, $H_3(y) = y^3 - 3y$, $H_4(y) = y^4 - 6y^2 + 3$, $H_5(y) = y^5 - 10y^3 + 15y$, and $H_6(y) = y^6 - 15y^4 + 45y^2 - 15$. The final form of the $p(x)$ is,

$$p(x) = O(x) \left[1 - c_3 \left[s^3 - 3s \right] + c_4 \left[s^4 - 6s^2 + 3 \right] - c_5 \left[s^5 - 10s^3 + 15s \right] + c_6 \left[s^6 - 15s^4 + 45s^2 - 15 \right] + \dots \right] \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where } s = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma} \text{ and } O(x) = \frac{1}{(2\pi\sigma^2)^{1/2}\sigma} e^{-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}}$$

3. Gram-Charlier Neural Network (GCNN) using Gram-Charlier Series Expansion Without Parzen's Windowing Technique.

For this classifier, an estimate of the underlying probability density function is formed from the training samples using Gram-Charlier series expansion. This estimated pdf and a priori probabilities are used to form a maximum likelihood classifier.

3.1. Gram-Charlier Neural Network (GCNN) (scalar sample case)

For this classifier, it is assumed that the density function $p(x)$ has zero mean ($\mu = 0$), and x_i 's are samples from the same random variable X . Thus, the conditional density function $p(x|H_i)$ of X under the i^{th} hypotheses H_i is given by

$$p(x|H_i) = \frac{1}{(2\pi\sigma^2)^{1/2}} e^{-\frac{(x)^2}{2\sigma^2}} * \left[1 - c_3^i \left[\left(\frac{x}{\sigma}\right)^3 - 3\left(\frac{x}{\sigma}\right) \right] + c_4^i \left[\left(\frac{x}{\sigma}\right)^4 - 6\left(\frac{x}{\sigma}\right)^2 + 3 \right] - c_5^i \left[\left(\frac{x}{\sigma}\right)^5 - 10\left(\frac{x}{\sigma}\right)^3 + 15\left(\frac{x}{\sigma}\right) \right] + c_6^i \left[\left(\frac{x}{\sigma}\right)^6 - 15\left(\frac{x}{\sigma}\right)^4 + 45\left(\frac{x}{\sigma}\right)^2 - 15 \right] \right] \quad (3)$$

The coefficients $c_0^i, c_1^i, \dots, c_6^i$ are to be calculated using the input scalar samples of the i^{th} class using equations in section 2.1 and as further explained in the training section (3.3) below.

3.2. Architecture of the GCNN (scalar sample case)

The overall functional block diagram of GCNN classifier is shown in Figure 1. If it is needed to classify L hypothesis $H_0, H_1, H_2, \dots, H_{L-1}$, then Figure 1 will consist of L subsections, one for each hypothesis. These subsections have the same architecture and function. As an example, one of the subsections is described in Figure 2. For hypothesis H_i , the first hidden layer in the i^{th} subsection adapts the weights w_{ik} to be equal to the corresponding coefficients c_i 's calculated using the input training samples belonging to class H_i . The nodes at the second hidden layer produce $p(x|H_i)$. The outputs of appropriate nodes of this layer for all classes are sent to the output layer for decision making. Training and testing processes are further discussed in sections (3.3 and 3.4 respectively).

3.3. Training of the GCNN (scalar sample case)

Training of the GCNN is accomplished as follows: It is assumed that all the training samples for all the classes H_0, H_1, \dots, H_{L-1} are available before the start of training. The training samples belonging to the class H_i are used to calculate the corresponding coefficients $c_0^i, c_1^i, \dots, c_6^i$ for this class as follows: Each subsection of the network is trained by using a modified Kohonen's learning law with the training samples of specified class. The training algorithm for the i^{th} , $i = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, L-1$ class consists of the following steps:

(1) Read all training samples of class H_i .

(2) calculate the noncentral moments $m_u^i = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N x_{ik}^u$, $u = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6$, from the input training samples x_{ik} 's.

(3) calculate the variance $(\sigma^2)^i = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N x_{ik}^2 - m_1^i$.

(4) calculate the central moments α_j^i 's using the calculated noncentral moments m_u using equations in section 2.1.

(5) calculate the coefficients c_u^i 's.

The final values of the trained weights are $w_u^{H_i} = c_u^{H_i}$, $u = 3, 4, 5, 6$. This process is repeated for all classes H_i , $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, L-1$. Once the training is completed, the GCNN is ready to be used at almost real time processing speed.

3.4. Testing of the GCNN (scalar sample case)

After the GCNN is trained, it is tested as follows:

(1) present the test input samples x .

(2) find $i=1$ for which $f(x|H_i)$ is the highest.

(3) Declare that the input sample belongs to the class H_i .

The performance of the proposed GCNN has been evaluated in terms of probability of correct classification over a large number of trials using syntetic radar data. The results are discussed in section 5.1.

4. Generalized Probabilistic Neural Network (GPNN) using Gram-Charlier

Series Expansion (GCSE) With Parzen's Windowing Technique. (scalar sample case)

4.1. Analytical Basis

In Parzen's windowing technique, a pdf $f(x)$ of a distribution is estimated by

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{\sigma} p[x-x_i], \quad (4)$$

where $p[x-x_i]$ is a density function shifted by x_i 's, the samples from actual density function. The samples x_i 's are assumed to be ergodic so that the ensemble average equals an appropriate time average. For the generalized probabilistic neural network (GPNN) with a Gram-Charlier series expansion (GCSE), the density function $p(x)$ in equation (4) is taken as density function given by equation (2). Thus, $f(x)$, the estimate of the actual density function is given by

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{N\sigma} \sum_{i=1}^N p[x-x_i] = \frac{1}{N\sigma} [p(x-x_1) + p(x-x_2) + \dots + p(x-x_N)] \quad (5)$$

The architecture of a neural network based system that will generate the density function $f(x)$ according to equation (5) is discussed in the section 4.2. The density function $f(x)$ in equation (5) involves N training samples (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N) . Equation (5) provides $f(x|H_i)$ when the training samples are from class H_i , $i=0, 1, 2, \dots, L-1$.

4.2. Architecture of the Generalized Probabilistic Neural Network (GPNN) (scalar sample case)

The overall architecture is shown in Figure 3. If it is needed to classify L classes of hypotheses $H_0, H_1, H_2, \dots, H_{L-1}$ then Figure 3 consists of L separate subsections, one for each hypothesis. These subsections are similar in architecture and function and hence only one such subsection (e.g. the subsection for H_0) is shown in Figure 4 and is described below. In Figure 4, the nodes at the second hidden layer produce $p(x-x_i)'s$; $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, where N is the number of samples in the training set, using equation (2). The outputs of appropriate nodes of this layer are added (at the nodes of the summation layer), using equation (5), to produce $f(x|H_0)$.

The terms like $p(x-x_i)$ in equation (5) are further elaborated in equation (6) (using equations in section 2.1).

$$p(x-x_i) = \frac{1}{(2\pi\sigma^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} e^{-\left[\frac{(x-x_i)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right]} \left[1 - c_3 \left[\left[\frac{x-x_i}{\sigma} \right]^3 - 3 \left[\frac{x-x_i}{\sigma} \right] \right] + c_4 \left[\left[\frac{x-x_i}{\sigma} \right]^4 - 6 \left[\frac{x-x_i}{\sigma} \right]^3 + 3 \right] \right. \\ \left. - c_5 \left[\left[\frac{x-x_i}{\sigma} \right]^5 - 10 \left[\frac{x-x_i}{\sigma} \right]^3 + 15 \left[\frac{x-x_i}{\sigma} \right] \right] + c_6 \left[\left[\frac{x-x_i}{\sigma} \right]^6 - 15 \left[\frac{x-x_i}{\sigma} \right]^4 + 45 \left[\frac{x-x_i}{\sigma} \right]^2 - 15 \right] \right] \quad (6)$$

4.3. Training of the GPNN (scalar sample case)

Each subsection of the network is trained by using a modified Kohonen's learning law with the training samples of a specified class. The training algorithm for the l^{th} subsection consists of the following steps:

- (1) Apply the training samples of the l^{th} class.
- (2) calculate the coefficients c_u^l $u=3,4,5,6$ using the training samples of the l^{th} class.
- (3) set $w_{lk} = x_{lk}$, $k=1,2,3,\dots,N$.
- (4) continue for $l=0,1,2,3,\dots,L-1$ sections. These sections are trained similarly using the training samples for relevant class. So that after training $w_{lk} = x_{lk}$, $l=0,1,2,\dots,L-1$, $k=1,2,\dots,N$.

4.4. Testing of the GPNN (scalar sample case)

Once the GPNN training is completed, it is ready to be used in almost real time. The testing of the network is performed in the following steps:

- (1) present the input sample $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_N)$ to the network.
- (2) calculate the $f(x|H_l)$, $l=0,1,2,\dots,L-1$.
- (3) determine the value of $l = j$ for which $f(x|H_j)$ is the highest.
- (4) Declare that the input sample belongs to the class H_j .

5. (Application): Radar Target Detection Using Probabilistic Neural Networks

The previous two sections 3 and 4 presented GCNN and GPNN classifiers. These algorithms have possible application in many areas. An important area of application of these proposed neural network based classifiers is in radar target detection in which the background noise and clutter are non-Gaussian. Next, we will examine application of GCNN, GPNN, PNN based Bayesian, and Backpropagation classifiers to radar target detection. The performances of these classifiers are evaluated and compared by computer simulation.

In radar environments, Weibull density function represents a good model of the non-Gaussian background noise. Thus, for practical reasons, the simulation of NNs (GPNN, GCNN, Backpropagation, and Bayesian classifier) have been performed with Weibull distributed background noise. The results of simulation are shown as plots of probability of detection versus Signal-to-Noise

Ratios (SNR).

5.1 Discussion of Simulation Results

It is observed from Figure 5 that for Gaussian noise both GCNN and GPNN outperforms Bayesian and BP classifier for SNR greater than -9 dB. Also, GCNN achieves $P_D \geq 0.9$ for $\text{SNR} \geq 3$ dB. Both BP and Bayesian P_D cannot go above 0.8, and highest value of P_D for BP is 0.82 if $\text{SNR} \geq 20$ dB. Thus shows promise of good performance by GCNN and GPNN for Gaussian noise. It should also be mentioned that this performance of GCNN and GPNN (scalar sample case) is also better than typical linear or matched filter classifiers.

Figure 6 shows performance of these classifiers in Weibull noise ($\alpha = 0.5$). Here the GCNN and GPNN performs as well as BP. However, performance of Bayesian classifier is almost constant at $P_D = 0.5$. Further performance evaluations have been done. However, due to space limitation, the results are being presented in a companion paper [4].

6. Conclusions

Two new probabilistic neural networks (GCNN and GPNN) have been formulated, simulated and evaluated. As seen from simulated results the GCNN and GPNN perform well in Gaussian and non-Gaussian noises. These classifiers works better than BP and Bayesian classifiers in many noise conditions. Thus the GCNN and GPNN show promise of good performance in Gaussian and several non-Gaussian noise environments.

7. References

1. D.E. Rumelhart, and et. al,' Parallel Distributed Processing, vol. 1: Foundations,' The MIT Press, Cambridge, Mass. and London, England, 1986.
2. D.F. Specht,' Probabilistic Neural Networks For Classification, Mapping, or Associative Memory,' Proc. of IEEE International Conference on Neural Networks, July 1988, vol. 1, pp. 525-532.
3. E. Parzen,' On estimation of a probability density function and mode,' Ann. Math. Stat., Vol. 33, pp. 1065-1076, Sept. 1962.
4. M. Kim, and M. Arozullah,' Neural Network Based Optimum Radar Target Detection In Non-Gaussian Noise', submitted to the IEEE International Joint Conference on Neural Networks to be held in Baltimore. June 1992.

Figure 1: The GCNN (scalar sample case) overall block diagram.

Figure 2: The GCNN (scalar sample case) realization of $p(x|H)$

Figure 3: The GPNN (scalar sample case) overall block diagram.

Figure 4: The GPNN (scalar sample case) realization of $\sum P(x-x_i | H_i)$

Figure 5: Performances of NNs for target detection in Gaussian noise (scalar case).

Figure 6: Performances of NNs for target detection in Weibull noise ($\alpha=0.5$) case (scalar case).